

The Language and Linguistics of Seidr. The Language and Linguistics of the Shades.

English word	Seidr word
The	Tidnae
Language	Laenguae
Of	Oeftae
Magic	Maegnae

Language > Word that starts with the letter A:

English word	Seidr word
Abacus	Aebaectinae
Abandoned	Aednoednae
Abdominal	Aedoemdaelae
Abhorrency	Aebhaena
Abnormal	Aebnoctnae
Abominable	Aedoembaebae
About	Aebodnae
Abrasion	Aebraescnae
Abruption	Aebrueptnae
Absentee	Abscaentae
Absolute	Aebsoeltnae
Absorb	Aebsaescae
Abstract	Aebstrascae
Absurd	Aesbuda
Abundant	Aebundnae
Academy	Aecedemiae
Acceleration	Aeceleraetnae
Acceptance	Aeceptaenae
Access	Aeccesnae
Accident	Ascidaendae

Language > Word that starts with F:

English word	Seidr word
Fire	Feignae

Language > Word that starts with M:

English word	Seidr word
Man	Maenae

Language > Word that starts with W:

English word	Seidr word
Woman	Etinae

Linguistics > Word that starts with the letter A:

English word	Seidr word
A	Aenae

Linguistics > Assorted:

English word	Seidr word
's/s (plural)	'nidnae/nidnae
-ed/ed	Idnae
-ing/ing	Ignae
-y/ie	eie